

Experimental Evaluation of a Heat Pump-Latent Storage System for Increasing Renewable Share of the Residential Stock

V. PALOMBA^(a), S. VARVAGIANNIS^(b), E. MONOKROUSOU^(b), B. NITSCH^(c), N. BARMPARITSAS^(d), A. BONANNO^(a), G.E. DINO^(a), A. LEONTARITIS^(b), A. STREHLOW^(c), S. KARELLAS^(b), A. FRAZZICA^(a), L.F. CABEZA^(e)

^(a)Istituto di Tecnologie Avanzate per l'Energia "Nicola Giordano", CNR ITAE, Messina, Italy

^(b)Lab. of Steam Boilers and Thermal Plants, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

^(c)AKG Verwaltungsgesellschaft mbH, Am Hohlen Weg 31, 34369 Hofgeismar, Germany

^(d)Daikin Air conditioning Greece, Ag. Konstantinou str. 50 15124 Maroussi, Athens, Greece

^(e)GREiA Research Group, INSPIRES Research Centre, Universitat de Lleida, Lleida, Spain

ABSTRACT

In the present work, the integration of a three-fluids heat exchanger in the evaporator of a reversible heat pump is evaluated. The heat exchanger includes internally finned passages for the refrigerant of the heat pump cycle and for the heat transfer fluid (water/glycol mixture) and externally finned passages for Phase Change Material (PCM). The selected PCM is a commercial paraffin (RT4) with nominal melting point of 4 °C. The operation of the integrated heat pump with latent storage under typical cooling season conditions in Mediterranean warm climates were evaluated through an experimental campaign at CNR. The effect of operating modes and operational conditions was identified. During charge, the variable speed of the compressor was found to yield the maximum effect on storage dynamics, whereas during discharge the prevalent effect is that of the heat transfer fluid flow rate. Based on the outcomes of measurement, a critical design review and control strategy improvement were carried out.

Keywords: latent storage, refrigeration, heat exchanger, experimental.

1. INTRODUCTION

Energy consumption in buildings accounts for 37% of the total energy demand in the EU [1]. Accordingly, decarbonization path should pass from the reduction of emissions from the building stock. For this reason, several national and international regulations have been issued to promote the energy efficiency in buildings, deriving from the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) issued by the EU. To do so, different strategies have been proposed over the years, such as improvement of building materials (i.e. facades materials, thermal insulation) and the functionalization of building materials [2]. In addition, several active methodologies were proposed with the idea of improving the heating and cooling systems, by enhancing the efficiency of the heating and cooling devices [3], implementing smart control strategies [4–6] and integrating innovative solutions at system level [7,8]. However, effort is still needed, especially with the aim of realizing systems that can drastically increase self-consumption, towards a 100% renewable energy scenario for the building stock [9–11]. In this context, the EU-funded project HYBUILD [12] has developed and tested an innovative energy system based on a hybrid electrical/thermal storage to maximize the use of solar energy at building level. In the present paper, the description of the system is presented, as well as the main results obtained in lab-controlled conditions.

2. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The investigated system consists of a reversible heat pump embedding a latent storage system. The latent storage is realised by means of a 3-fluids heat exchanger with Refrigerant-PCM-Water circuits (RPW-HEX). The chosen PCM is a commercial paraffin with nominal melting temperature of 4 °C. The latent storage can be charged by direct evaporation of the refrigerant of the heat pump and is discharged by circulating water inside the heat exchanger. In addition, parallel mode (i.e. contemporary charge and discharge of the storage) can be exploited if needed. The heat exchanger is described in detail in [13] and consists of an aluminium flat

tube heat exchanger with alternated channels for the refrigerant and the water. The PCM is instead inserted in the space between the fins. Since it is in contact with both the refrigerant and the water channels, it can be charged from the R410A and discharged by exchanging heat with the water loop. A picture of the system installed in the testing stand at CNR ITAE is shown in [Figure 1](#).

The refrigerant circuit is typical of a conventional water chiller design, consisting of a hermetic scroll compressor, a Thermostatic Expansion Valve and two plate heat exchangers, the evaporator and the condenser. No 4way valve is installed and thus, if heating is needed, the hydraulic circuits of the evaporator and the condenser need to be switched, to reverse the operation. The RPW-HEX actually replaces the standard evaporator in cooling mode. In order to maintain the option to operate the heat pump with the standard evaporator (essential in heating mode), bypass loops have been implemented in both the refrigerant and the water-glycol circuits. In the hydraulic side, a 3way ball valve (2) connects either the standard evaporator or the RPW-HEX to the water-glycol supply pipeline. Lastly, since there is a large discrepancy between the refrigerant charge needed for the RPW-HEX and the standard evaporator, a liquid receiver at the exit of the condenser was installed.

Figure 1 integration of the latent thermal storage in the heat pump – focus on refrigerant circuit. 1: condenser, 2: standard evaporator, 3: compressor, 4: liquid receiver, 5: expansion valve, 6: RPW-HEX

3. EXPERIMENTAL FACILITIES AND TESTING CONDITIONS

The experimental facilities used for the testing of the system are described in detail in [14]. The testing rig at CNR-ITAE mainly consists of three storages, corresponding to three different thermal levels. A high-temperature level, obtained by using two heaters, a gas heater and an electric one, connected to a 1.5 m³ storage. It is usually exploited for driving thermally-driven chillers (in this case it was not employed). An intermediate temperature level, which simulates the ambient heat sink by means of an electric chiller connected to a 1 m³ storage. A low-temperature level, which simulates the heat source for evaporation by means of a 0.75 m³ storage with immersed thermal resistances. All the piping of the testing rig is insulated with polyurethane foam and aluminium external cover. Data acquisition and control are done through cDAQ National Instrument hardware and LabVIEW software. Uncertainty of measurement calculated is 5% for the cooling power and 6-8% for the EER. The following testing conditions were chosen:

- Operation of the heat pump with the standard evaporator. In this case, tests were aimed at the evaluation of the cooling power and EER for different speeds of the compressor, in order to have information on the possible performance in the various cases.
- Charge of the RPW-HEX, at different speed of the compressor and with different heat transfer fluid (HTF) inlet temperatures, with the aim of identifying the amount of energy that can be stored in the system.
- Discharge of the RPW-HEX, at different HTF inlet temperatures and flow rates, to identify the optimal parameters for the operation of this component, in view of installation in demo sites.

- Parallel mode, i.e. contemporary charge and discharge of the RPW-HEX.

4. TESTING RESULTS

4.1 Operation with the standard evaporator

The tests with the standard evaporator were done according to the following protocol:

- Start of the testing rig and set of temperature levels and flow rates desired;
- Start of the heat pump and, once steady-state operation is reached, recording of the test for at least 10 minutes;
- Stop of the test.

The results of the testing campaign are reported in Figure 2 as a complete performance map. It shows cooling capacity for three different Heat Transfer Fluid (HTF) inlet to the evaporator, i.e. 9, 12, 15 °C and for all the compressor supply frequencies tested. As is it possible to notice, the values are distributed along decreasing bands, each band corresponding to a compressor frequency. The cooling power is obviously higher for higher compressor driving frequency and, for each one of them, decreases with increasing condenser inlet and with decreasing evaporator inlet.

Figure 2: overall map of cooling capacity for the operation of the heat pump with standard evaporator.

Figure 3 shows the EER of the heat pump, i.e. the ratio between the cooling supplied and the energy consumed for compressor operation as a function of operating temperatures and compressor speed. Similarly to the case of the cooling capacity, the EER decreases with increasing condenser inlet temperature and with decreasing evaporator inlet temperature. However, it is interesting to notice that, for the lower condensing temperature, i.e. below 32°C, reducing the compressor speed makes the heat pump work more efficiently. Indeed, as it is reported in Figure 3, in this case, the EER for operation at 25 Hz is higher than for the operation at higher compressor speed.

Figure 3: map of performance of the compression heat pump -EER.

4.2 Charge of the RPW-HEX

Charging tests were done as follows:

- Temperature levels, compressor speed and flow rates were set in the testing rig;
- Water at 15°C was circulated into the RPW-HEX, to have homogeneous and repeatable initial conditions.
- Heat pump was started and the test recorded;

Charge was considered finished when the temperature of the PCM_{down} sensor is -2.5°C.

Figure 4 shows the energy supplied during charging tests at different condenser inlet temperatures and different driving frequencies of the compressor. It is possible to notice that the energy supplied is between 2 kWh and 2.5 kWh. The higher amount of energy supplied for higher condenser inlet temperatures and for lower compressor speed is due to the higher duration of the test, with a consequent more marked effect of thermal losses. It is then possible to state that the amount of energy that the RPW-HEX can store is 2.0-2.3 kWh.

Figure 4: energy supplied during charge of the RPW-HEX as a function of condensation temperature and compressor driving frequency.

4.3 Discharge of the RPW-HEX

Discharge tests were done as follows:

- Setting of temperature and flow rates of the HTF in the testing rig;
- Opening of the connection between the testing rig and the RPW-HEX;
- Start of the test and of the recording;
- The test is stopped when $PCM_{up}=HTF_{in}$ and $PCM_{down}=HTF_{in}-2$ K.

Figure 5 shows the energy discharged as a function of flow rate of the HTF in the RPW-HEX and after different charges, done with condenser inlet temperature ranging from 20 °C to 40 °C. It is clear from the experimental results that the optimal flow rate for the operation of the RPW-HEX in discharge mode is 10-12 kg/min, corresponding to 6.0-7.2 m³/h. Indeed, lower flow rates do not allow a good exploitation of the energy stored, because the discharge is much longer (around 40 min at 0.11 kg/s against 20-30 min at 0.17 kg/min) and the effect of thermal losses is higher. On the contrary, the higher flow rates lead to a reduction in the ΔT at the HEX, in turn reducing the exploitable energy for practical purposes. Instead, as shown in Figure 5, the temperature at which charge occurred, as long as the charge is complete, does not significantly influence the discharged energy. It is necessary to state that all the tests here presented are done without any stand-by period between charge and discharge, in order to avoid any effect of the thermal losses during this period.

Figure 5: discharged energy as a function of flow rate for $Evap_{in}=12^{\circ}C$.

Figure 6 shows the discharge power as a function of flow rate. All the tests are done at a constant HTF inlet temperature ($12^{\circ}C$) and without any stand-by period between charge and discharge. As it is intuitive, increasing the flow rate increases the discharge power, passing from about 3-4 kW at 0.12 kg/s to 5-6 kW at 0.18-0.25 kg/s. As previously stated, however, increasing the flow rate reduces the energy recoverable and therefore an optimal condition has to be sought.

Figure 6: discharge power as a function of flow rate for $Evap_{in}=12^{\circ}C$.

4.4 Temperature distribution measurements with IR camera

A set of measurements was carried out with a FLIR A655sc IR camera, with the aim of identifying temperature distribution and thermal gradients during charging and discharging. As exemplary case, Figure 7 shows some of the frames recorded for a charge/discharge test where charge and discharged were carried out in sequence, without any storage time in between. Discharge is carried out with HTF inlet of $15^{\circ}C$ and 0.2 kg/s flow rate.

A clear gradient both in transversal and longitudinal direction is identifiable, which is of about 7 K in transversal direction, with the inlet side of the refrigerant at a lower temperature, and up to 20 K at the end of the charge process in longitudinal direction. Accordingly, during discharge, the upper part of the storage reaches the temperature of the HTF faster than the remaining portion of the storage. It is possible to notice, in the frame taken after 100 s from the beginning of discharge, the gradient in the transversal direction: the uppermost layers are colder than the middle ones, that correspond to the height where the pipe for the HTF is located. Afterwards, the process continues by gradual melting from the upper part down to the bottom of the storage. The gradient in the longitudinal direction in this case is evident only in the first 200 s and subsequently is much lower than during the charge process.

Figure 7: charge and discharge of the RPW-HEX visualized with IR camera

A detail of a charging process is shown in Figure 8, where it is possible to notice how the heat exchange during charge occurs through the refrigerant passages, that are clearly highlighted and represent the coldest spots of the HEX.

Figure 8: detail of a charging process.

4.5 Parallel charge/discharge of the RPW-HEX

The temperature trends for the parallel operation, i.e. simultaneous charge and discharge of the RPW-HEX during a reference test in all the circuits are presented in Figure 9. The test is run in “steady-state” mode, meaning that the PCM has already been charged to the operating temperature for the parallel mode, which is $LT_{comp,in}=5^{\circ}\text{C}$, ensuring that part of the PCM is already in liquid state. What is interesting to notice is that the stratification inside the PCM is in the order of 3 K, with the lower values for the PCM4 temperatures, i.e. the closest point to refrigerant inlet.

Figure 9: temperatures in the PCM circuit for a parallel charge/discharge operation.

At the same time, a constant cooling supply to the user is guaranteed, which is in the order of 2/3 of the cooling energy delivered under the same operating conditions during the operation with the standard evaporator.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper, the results of the experimental testing of an integrated latent storage with heat pump system are reported. The latent storage is realised through a three-fluids heat exchanger, to maximise the compactness and the heat transfer efficiency. The extensive testing campaign under different operating modes highlighted the possibility, with the investigated layout, to deliver cooling energy to an end-user improving the overall efficiency and flexibility in operation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 768824 (HYBUILD).

NOMENCLATURE

<i>cond</i>	condenser	<i>EER</i>	Energy Efficiency Ratio
<i>HEX</i>	Heat Exchanger	<i>HTF</i>	Heat Transfer Fluid
<i>in</i>	inlet	<i>out</i>	outlet
<i>PCM</i>	Phase Change Material	<i>RPW</i>	Refrigerant-PCM-Water

REFERENCES

- [1] Action E. Implementing the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), Featuring country reports. EU Publications Office; 2016.
- [2] Gullbrekken L, Grynning S, Gaarder J, Gullbrekken L, Grynning S, Gaarder JE. Thermal Performance of Insulated Constructions—Experimental Studies. *Buildings* 2019;9:49. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings9020049>.
- [3] Rony R, Yang H, Krishnan S, Song J, Rony RU, Yang H, et al. Recent Advances in Transcritical CO₂ (R744) Heat Pump System: A Review. *Energies* 2019;12:457. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12030457>.
- [4] Bee E, Prada A, Baggio P, Bee E, Prada A, Baggio P. Demand-Side Management of Air-Source Heat Pump and Photovoltaic Systems for Heating Applications in the Italian Context. *Environments* 2018;5:132. <https://doi.org/10.3390/environments5120132>.
- [5] Dengiz T, Jochem P, Fichtner W. Demand response with heuristic control strategies for modulating heat pumps. *Appl Energy* 2019;238:1346–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2018.12.008>.
- [6] Pospíšil J, Špiláček M, Kudela L. Potential of predictive control for improvement of seasonal coefficient of performance of air source heat pump in Central European climate zone. *Energy* 2018;154:415–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2018.04.131>.
- [7] Millar M-A, Burnside N, Yu Z, Millar M-A, Burnside NM, Yu Z. District Heating Challenges for the UK. *Energies* 2019;12:310. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12020310>.
- [8] Zhang L, Li F, Sun B, Zhang C, Zhang L, Li F, et al. Integrated Optimization Design of Combined Cooling, Heating, and Power System Coupled with Solar and Biomass Energy. *Energies* 2019;12:687. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12040687>.
- [9] Hvelplund F, Krog L, Nielsen S, Terkelsen E, Madsen KB. Policy paradigms for optimal residential heat savings in a transition to 100% renewable energy systems. *Energy Policy* 2019;134:110944. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENPOL.2019.110944>.
- [10] Thellufsen JZ, Lund H, Sorknæs P, Østergaard PA, Chang M, Drysdale D, et al. Smart energy cities in a 100% renewable energy context. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2020;129:109922. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.109922>.
- [11] Child M, Kemfert C, Bogdanov D, Breyer C. Flexible electricity generation, grid exchange and storage for the transition to a 100% renewable energy system in Europe. *Renew Energy* 2019;139:80–101. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RENENE.2019.02.077>.
- [12] HYBUILD n.d. <http://www.hybuild.eu/>.
- [13] Palomba V, Bonanno A, Brunaccini G, Aloisio D, Sergi F, Dino GE, et al. Hybrid Cascade Heat Pump and Thermal-Electric Energy Storage System for Residential Buildings: Experimental Testing and Performance Analysis. *Energies* 2021;14:2580. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14092580>.
- [14] Dino GE, Palomba V, Nowak E, Frazzica A. Experimental characterization of an innovative hybrid thermal-electric chiller for industrial cooling and refrigeration application. *Appl Energy* 2021;281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2020.116098>.